

THE ESTIMATION OF TOTAL VITAMIN C IN FOOD-STUFFS.

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Elsewhere (Guha and Pal, *Nature*, 1936, 137, 946) we have given evidence to show that in many plant food-stuffs ascorbic acid is present partly in the combined state, from which the vitamin can be released readily by heating. It has been possible to extract this substance from several food-stuffs, which we have proposed to call "ascorbigen" for convenience. It has become clear from these results that the usual method of trichloroacetic acid extraction of food-stuffs, which has been almost universally used in the estimation of vitamin C by the Tillmans-Harris technique, would give low values for total ascorbic acid (combined and free) in many cases, where appreciable quantities of ascorbigen are present. From the nutritional standpoint it is necessary to know the amount of the total ascorbic acid, as we have previously observed (Guha and Pal, *loc. cit.*) that 0.2 % hydrochloric acid, which is normally present in gastric juice, is capable of splitting an aqueous extract of ascorbigen. It would appear, therefore, that many results so far recorded about the vitamin C content of food-stuffs, would in many instances give an erroneous idea about the total ascorbic acid available for nutritional purposes. Accordingly it was considered desirable to work out a method, by which the total ascorbic acid in food-stuffs might be estimated. The most reliable method must obviously be such as would split all the ascorbigen present and prevent the oxidation of ascorbic acid and thus give the highest value for ascorbic acid.

It should be stated that there is some controversy going on about the existence or otherwise of combined ascorbic acid in plant food materials (Mack, *Nature*, 1936, 138, 505; Levy, *ibid.*, 1936, 138, 933), but our evidence, which will be presented in greater detail later, shows almost conclusively that a reducing substance is released from cabbage by heat, which reduces the indophenol indicator like ascorbic acid. We are at present carrying out biological experiments to test whether this reducing substance is actually vitamin C. But so far as the object of the present paper is concerned, here it is intended to show merely that under certain conditions the value of ascorbic acid obtained is much higher than that obtained by the usual method. And if the titrimetric technique is considered to give the ascorbic acid value specifically, then

the method elaborated in the present paper would appear to give the highest figure.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Determination of Total Ascorbic Acid without Reduction.

Five widely different varieties of food-stuffs were selected for study: *patol* (*Tricosanthes dioxia*), cabbage, potato, guava and onion. 10 G. of each of the fresh food-stuffs were taken for each treatment, finely disintegrated in a mortar with washed sea-sand and mixed up with the appropriate extractant. The mixture was then centrifuged and the centrifugate diluted to 100 c.c. The titrations were carried out with the 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol indicator by the method described before (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 30). Figures given in each table indicate the values obtained by the different treatments with the same sample of food-stuff. All experiments were carried out with three samples and in the tables all the three values are given. The experiments of each table are comparable among themselves as they were carried out under as identical conditions as possible.

(a) Table I gives the results obtained by treatment with trichloroacetic acid and hydrochloric acid of different concentrations for different periods. These indicate that treatment of 10 g. of food-stuff with 50 c.c. of 10% hydrochloric acid for 1 hour in CO₂ gives the highest figure for vitamin C, except in the case of the guava, which gives the best results with trichloroacetic acid.

(b) Table II gives the results obtained by treatment with 10% hydrochloric acid in CO₂ for different periods and also by treatment with 20% hydrochloric acid in CO₂. These figures show that the concentration of the acid remaining the same, the amount of ascorbic acid gradually diminishes with the increase of time; 20% acid apparently causes a loss except in the case of guava. Treatment with 10% hydrochloric acid for 1 hour in CO₂, therefore, seems to give the highest value in this group of experiments.

(c) In this set of experiments the effect of air, carbon dioxide and nitrogen on the value of ascorbic acid obtained in 10% hydrochloric acid solution was investigated. Nitrogen and CO₂ appear to be equally good, while there is a slight tendency to loss in air in one or two cases (Table III.)

(d) Finally, the results of treatment with 10% hydrochloric acid in CO₂ for 1 hour were compared with those obtained by heating the food-stuffs with water (50 c.c. per 10 g. of food-stuff) on a boiling water-bath for

different periods in air, in CO₂, and in nitrogen and then extracting with trichloroacetic acid in the usual way (Table IV).

Figures are given in mg. of ascorbic acid per g. of food-stuff in all the tables. 10 G. of food-stuffs were taken in each case.

TABLE I.

Food-stuff.	Trichloroacetic acid method.	50 C.c. of	50 C.c. of	50 C.c. of	50 C.c. of	50 C.c. of	50 C.c. of
		10% trichloroacetic acid,	1% HCl in CO ₂	5% HCl for 1 hour.	10% HCl	1% HCl in CO ₂ for 3 hrs.	5% HCl in CO ₂ for 2 hrs.
Patol	0.138	0.155	0.109	0.147	0.156	0.136	0.145
	0.134	0.150	0.112	0.146	0.151	0.136	0.150
	0.138	0.150	0.112	0.147	0.155	0.138	0.149
Cabbage.	0.425	0.495	0.320	0.362	0.400	0.277	0.365
	0.300	0.272	0.239	0.352	0.452	0.274	0.380
	0.320	0.300	0.258	0.371	0.426	0.278	0.350
Potato	0.163	0.179	0.131	0.192	0.242	0.148	0.212
	0.153	0.173	0.130	0.180	0.226	0.138	0.204
	0.158	0.175	0.127	0.187	0.232	0.145	0.208
Guava	0.908	0.906	0.813	0.865	0.886	0.671	0.806
	0.900	0.905	0.788	0.885	0.852	0.668	0.803
	0.904	0.903	0.802	0.904	0.929	0.674	0.803
Onion	0.165	0.175	0.140	0.160	0.184	0.077	0.160
	0.165	0.171	0.142	0.161	0.186	0.068	0.153
	0.167	0.173	0.141	0.165	0.183	0.071	0.155

TABLE II.

Food-stuff.	Trichloroacetic acid method.	Treatment with 50 c.c. of 10% HCl in CO ₂			50 C.c. of 20% HCl in CO ₂
		for 1 hr.	for 2 hrs.	for 3 hrs.	for 1 hr.
Patol	0.126	0.139	0.125	0.124	0.117
	0.128	0.147	0.129	0.127	0.122
	0.127	0.143	0.127	0.124	0.118
Cabbage	0.306	0.671	0.562	0.483	0.425
	0.315	0.600	0.520	0.416	0.350
	0.320	0.600	0.507	0.433	0.365
Potato	0.157	0.231	0.212	0.179	0.167
	0.160	0.226	0.206	0.176	0.170
	0.164	0.230	0.204	0.179	0.167
Guava	0.945	0.904	0.745	0.671	0.832
	1.040	0.945	1.040	0.800	1.040
	0.994	0.923	0.834	0.737	0.832
Onion	0.140	0.174	0.174	0.163	0.154
	0.152	0.179	0.166	0.159	0.151
	0.147	0.175	0.170	0.158	0.154

TABLE III.

Food-stuff.	Trichloroacetic acid method.	Treatment with 50 c.c. of 10% HCl in		
		CO ₂ for 1 hr.	N ₂ for 1 hr.	air for 1 hr.
Patol	0·126	0·139	0·140	0·142
	0·128	0·147	0·145	0·146
	0·127	0·143	0·141	0·145
Cabbage	0·277	0·547	0·507	0·500
	0·292	0·600	0·547	0·533
	0·320	0·600	0·520	0·483
Potato	0·157	0·231	0·226	0·226
	0·160	0·226	0·221	0·231
	0·164	0·230	0·222	0·227
Guava	0·945	0·904	0·945	0·866
	1·040	0·945	0·951	0·863
	0·994	0·923	0·945	0·868
Onion	0·140	0·174	0·173	0·176
	0·152	0·179	0·175	0·168
	0·147	0·175	0·177	0·165

TABLE IV.

	Trichloroacetic acid method.	Treatment with 50 c.c. of water on boiling water-bath in				50 C. c. of 10% HCl in CO ₂ for 1 hr.	
		N ₂ for 10 mins.	air for 10 mins.	N ₂ for 15 mins.	CO ₂ for 15 mins.		N ₂ for 20 mins.
Patol	0·117	0·170	0·130	0·193	0·199	0·177	0·133
	0·128	0·181	0·128	0·201	0·201	0·184	0·138
	0·135	0·192	0·130	0·218	0·209	0·193	0·144
Cabbage	0·266	0·483	0·507	0·562	0·547	0·521	0·325
	0·281	0·547	0·408	0·671	0·630	0·407	0·341
	0·263	0·433	0·353	0·507	0·500	0·380	0·306
Potato	0·160	0·270	0·245	0·302	0·297	0·260	0·225
	0·150	0·271	0·247	0·304	0·295	0·267	0·225
	0·155	0·278	0·250	0·312	0·300	0·270	0·229
Guava	0·905	0·906	0·534	0·904	0·890	0·670	0·864
	0·904	0·903	0·531	0·901	0·887	0·675	0·868
	0·904	0·904	0·534	0·903	0·890	0·670	0·866
Onion	0·113	0·120	0·0710	0·120	0·110	0·117	0·115
	0·115	0·121	0·0714	0·121	0·119	0·119	0·117
	0·114	0·120	0·0713	0·125	0·122	0·119	0·117

Determination of Total Ascorbic Acid after Reduction

In the foregoing section the relative effects of different treatments on the ascorbic acid values of five different plant materials have been investigated, with reference to the question of estimation of the free ascorbic acid and of the ascorbic acid released from combination. It would seem, however, that the question of the naturally occurring dehydroascorbic acid should also be taken into consideration in order to get a true estimate of the total ascorbic acid from the nutritional standpoint, as dehydroascorbic acid does not reduce the dye but is known to be biologically potent. It is, therefore, necessary that the ascorbic acid values should be estimated after reduction of the reversibly oxidised ascorbic acid by some suitable means. In order, therefore, to estimate the total ascorbic acid, comprising (1) the free ascorbic acid (2) the ascorbic acid released from combination by heat and (3) the ascorbic acid formed by the reduction of the dehydroascorbic acid, the five food materials were investigated after reduction with hydrogen sulphide on a boiling water-bath. Table V gives the relative values obtained (1) by the usual method of extraction with trichloroacetic acid (Ghosh and Guha, *loc. cit.*), (2) by heating the aqueous suspension on a water-bath in CO_2 for 15 minutes, (3) by passing H_2S into the aqueous suspension for 30 minutes, the suspension being heated in H_2S for 15 minutes out of this total period of 30 minutes, and (4) by passing H_2S into the aqueous suspension for 30 minutes at room temperature (25°). Hydrogen sulphide was, of course, completely removed by a current of CO_2 or N_2 before titration. It will be observed that, although in the previous section, heating in CO_2 gave the highest result, higher figures are obtained even by cold treatment with H_2S , which indicates the presence of reversibly oxidised ascorbic acid in these materials. But still higher figures are obtained by treatment with H_2S in hot condition in the above five cases, except in guava. The difference between the values obtained by treatment with H_2S in the hot and cold conditions, incidentally, indicates the presence of ascorbigen especially in the cases of cabbage, *patol* and potato. However, considering all the different treatments, it is clear that the highest figures are obtained by treatment with H_2S in the hot condition. It should be mentioned that in these titrations, we have added 1 c.c. of *M*-formaldehyde (Mason, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, **86**, 623) and 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid to the dye before titration, in order to inhibit the effects of possible interfering substances.

In Table VI are given some figures obtained (1) by grinding the material under trichloroacetic acid, so as to inactivate the ascorbic acid oxidase as far

as possible, (2) by heating the cut pieces in aqueous suspension in CO_2 , (3) by treating the cut pieces in aqueous suspension with H_2S in the hot condition and (4) by first grinding up the cut pieces with sand and then heating in an atmosphere of H_2S as in experiment (3) In these experiments also the higher values were obtained by treating with H_2S in the hot condition and the fact that the values under (3) and (4) are identical show that it makes no difference whether the extraction is preceded by simple cutting up by scissors or by grinding with sand. It should be mentioned further that blank experiments with H_2S in the hot and cold conditions gave no values with the dye. The final method that we adopted is as follows:

The material (10 g.) was cut into small pieces, taken in a suspension of 50 c.c. of water and H_2S was passed into it. After 30-60 minutes, the suspension was heated under reflux on a boiling water-bath, while H_2S was being passed. Heating was continued for 15 minutes and then H_2S was removed completely (as tested by lead acetate paper) by a current of CO_2 or N_2 . The suspension was then treated with 2.5 c.c. of 20% trichloroacetic acid, the mixture filtered or centrifuged and the filtrate made up to 100 c.c. This solution was titrated against 0.5 c.c. of $M/10$ -2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol, to which 1 c.c. of M -formaldehyde and 1 c.c. of glacial acetic acid had been previously added. The titration should be finished within 1 minute.

TABLE V.

Food-stuffs.	Ascorbic acid by trichloroacetic acid extraction.	Heated on a water-bath with 50 c.c. of water for 15 mins. in CO_2 .	for 15 mins. in H_2S and H_2S removed by CO_2 or N_2 .	Treated with 50 c.c. of cold water; H_2S passed for 30 mins. and H_2S removed by CO_2 or N_2 .
Cabbage	0.305	0.358	0.866	0.472
	0.208	0.260	0.743	0.371
	0.346	0.433	0.945	0.577
Patol	0.176	0.189	0.495	0.352
	0.186	0.212	0.547	0.384
	0.253	0.290	0.611	0.452
Potato	0.106	0.114	0.346	0.260
	0.110	0.125	0.400	0.358
	0.112	0.126	0.410	0.365
Guava	1.040	1.040	1.300	1.300
	1.600	1.500	1.890	1.890
	1.040	1.040	1.300	1.300
Onion	0.165	0.182	0.241	0.212
	0.155	0.176	0.241	0.208
	0.160	0.181	0.239	0.210

TABLE VI.

Food-stuffs (10g.)	(1) Treatment under trichloro- acetic acid.	(2) The cut pieces heated with 50 c.c. of H ₂ O on a water-bath for 15 mins. in CO ₂ .	(3) The cut pieces heated with 50 c.c. of H ₂ O on a water-bath for 15 mins. in H ₂ S and H ₂ S removed by CO ₂ or N ₂ .	(4) The cut pieces ground up with sand and then heated with water in presence of H ₂ S as in expt. 3.
Cabbage	0'400	0'520	0'693	0'693
	0'650	0'750	0'866	0'866
Patol	0'433	0'495	0'611	0'611
	0'385	0'452	0'520	0'520
Potato	0'173	0'247	0'346	0'346
	0'176	0'267	0'358	0'358
Guava	1'500	1'500	1'890	1'890
	1'300	1'300	1'600	1'600
Onion	0'155	0'173	0'231	0'231
	0'165	0'182	0'247	0'247

DISCUSSION.

These results indicate that absolutely uniform results cannot be expected by the same treatment applied to widely different plant food-stuffs. Thus, while trichloroacetic acid treatment gives better results in the case of guava, hydrochloric acid gives higher values in other cases. Nor is there uniformity regarding the values obtained with different concentrations of hydrochloric acid. This does not seem surprising when it is considered that these food-stuffs contain perhaps many substances which might influence the behavior of vitamin C (free and combined) to various treatments and reagents. It should be mentioned that in cases where trichloroacetic acid and hydrochloric acid of different concentrations were used, blank experiments were carried out with the acids alone to see if they would decolourise the dye. It was found that if the titration was carried out within one minute under our conditions (Ghosh and Guha, *loc. cit.*) no material errors were introduced.

S U M M A R Y.

The general result of the investigation is that among the following methods (1) treatment with trichloroacetic acid, (2) allowing to stand with trichloroacetic and hydrochloric acids, (3) heating in CO_2 or N_2 for different periods, (4) treatment with H_2S in the cold and, (5) treatment with H_2S in the hot condition, the last method gave the highest value for ascorbic acid. This method would seem to give the total value of ascorbic acid comprising (a) the free vitamin, (b) the ascorbic acid which is released by heating, and (c) the reversibly oxidised ascorbic acid.

A method has thus been elaborated which gives the highest ascorbic acid value and it would seem that many food-stuffs investigated before require re-investigation by the new technique for a more correct estimation of ascorbic acid. Although in some cases, as in guava, treatment with H_2S in the hot and cold conditions might give the same result, still it would seem desirable to carry out the treatment with H_2S in the hot condition as a routine procedure. There is the possibility that this treatment might itself release some non-specific reducing substance. This has been to some extent guarded against by adding formaldehyde to the dye. In this investigation it is, of course, assumed that the titrimetric technique carried out under precise conditions gives the correct value for ascorbic acid and we are at present planning biological experiments to test this point further.

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